

Enhancing Student Learning Experiences Through Integrated Constructivist Pedagogical Models

Maimoona H. Al Abri ✉

Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Oman

Asma Y. Al Aamri ✉

Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Oman

Abdelrahman Mohamed Ahmed Elhaj ✉

Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Oman

Abstract

This study investigates the use of constructive pedagogy models to effectively engage students and enhance their learning experiences in college courses. Meaningful Online Learning attributes was used to redesign a face-to-face course in Sultan Qaboos University in Oman. The contemporary landscape of higher education is marked by a dynamic shift towards optimizing pedagogical approaches to meet diverse learning needs and preferences and to effectively engage students and enhance their learning experiences. Within this context, this research delves into the exploration of constructive pedagogy models as a means to actively engage students and elevate their learning experiences in the realm of college courses. A mixed-method approach was employed to conduct an exploratory case study, which involved the use of various instruments and sources such as a pre-course survey, a focus group discussion, and an analysis of the course based on the Meaningful Online Learning framework. This study lies in providing guidelines for faculty to redesign their courses using constructive approaches, particularly emphasizing the MOL attributes and to improve the quality of their courses. The results unveiled a positive correlation between the incorporation of Meaningful Online Learning attributes into the course redesign and the improvement of students' learning experiences. Furthermore, students exhibited the acquisition of novel skills and knowledge through the adaptation of assignments and learning activities associated with the course. Educators in higher education have to enhance their courses based on the MOL principles to effectively engage students in learning process and to design active and constructive courses that contribute to enhance students' learning success. The researcher recommends applying this approach and the obtained design principles to other courses for refinement purposes. Additionally, they suggest conducting a comparative study between a class with traditional pedagogy and a class with constructivist pedagogy. Implication of the finding of this study showed that it is important to design engaging learning experiences to gain students the required skill to compete globally and contribute effectively to their communities. That is, students are playing crucial roles in society's development especially in sustainable development. Further investigation is needed to refine and enhance the obtained principles and to share best practices of designing meaningful learning using innovative pedagogy models.

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Introduction

The contemporary landscape of higher education is marked by a dynamic shift towards optimizing pedagogical approaches to meet diverse learning needs and preferences and to effectively engage students and enhance their learning experiences. Within this context, this research delves into the exploration of constructive pedagogy models as a means to actively engage students and elevate their learning experiences in the realm of college courses.

In response to the Covid-19 pandemic, educational organizations worldwide were forced to transition from face-to-face classes to distance education and later to blended learning under various conditions. It was generally overwhelming for faculty in higher education institutions to adapt to emergency online teaching. However, through these teaching experiences, instructors have gained skills in utilizing the affordances of technology to support students' learning performance.

A study conducted in Oman during the spring and summer of 2020 emphasized the importance of utilizing instructional design principles in the context of online learning to mitigate various challenges encountered during this transition (Najah, Rao, & Al Qassabi, 2023). The researchers recognized the significance of aligning online teaching strategies with institutional goals and strategies, ensuring a harmonious integration of technology and pedagogy. One of the most prevalent challenges identified in this study was related to students' access to reliable internet connections, especially in remote areas where connectivity may be suboptimal. Overcoming this challenge necessitates innovative solutions, such as recording live online sessions and sharing video links with students, thus ensuring equitable access to educational content. However, not all challenges were technical. Some students resisted the virtual learning environment, citing its perceived inefficiency compared to traditional in-person teaching. They missed the nuances of face-to-face interactions like body language and spontaneous discussions. Additionally, reservations among students prevented the sharing of video feeds during live classes, making it challenging to gauge their engagement. From a teacher's perspective, maintaining student engagement became a top priority. This meant designing activities that would keep students actively participating in online sessions is important.

Returning to face-to-face teaching and learning presents opportunities to incorporate constructivist pedagogy into traditional education. The integration of technology into educational settings offers students the invaluable opportunity to receive instruction from internationally renowned experts, regardless of their physical location. To continue using technology in teaching and learning, instructors need to continually improve their skills and knowledge in delivering meaningful learning through adopting

constructivist pedagogy in their practices (Mosely, Harris, & Grushka, 2021). Consequently, instructors will be able to combine face-to-face classes and online learning effectively using the principles of constructivist pedagogy models.

Gupta, and Yadav (2023) asserted that when educators embrace technology more extensively, they can incorporate cutting-edge educational materials and the latest pedagogical approaches into their lessons. In this regard, the researchers emphasized that institutes should prioritize improving several key factors in teaching and learning practices, including technical support, learners' technological proficiency, faculty capabilities, learners' willingness to adopt new technologies, innovative course designs, and the provision of social support. These considerations are essential not only for educators but also for students and educational institutions, each playing a significant role in this transformative process.

In a study conducted by Alt (2015) that aimed to investigate the relationship between educational approaches based on constructivist theory and students' self-efficacy beliefs in higher education, 167 undergraduate students participated in a Problem-Based Learning (PBL) environment, informed by constructivist theory, and a traditional lecture-based environment. The results of the study indicated that students in the PBL course perceived the learning environment as more constructivist and reported higher academic self-efficacy compared to the lecture-based environment. As a result, there is a need for design principles that guide instructional designers and stakeholders in creating meaningful learning environments, considering all the factors mentioned above. This study utilized the principles of instructional design in terms of integrating MOL attributes and constructivist pedagogical models. These principles are discussed next.

Conceptual Framework

Meaningful learning refers to humans' ability to connect new concepts with pre-existing ones, leading to longer retention of knowledge compared to memorization (Vallori, 2014). The conceptual framework employed in this exploratory study is the MOL design framework, developed by Dabbagh, Marra, and Howland (2019). The MOL design framework promotes learning through active engagement and emphasizes the relationship between the three key components of pedagogical models for online learning (instructional strategies, learning activities, and learning technologies) and the five attributes of meaningful learning. The MOL design framework serves as a guide for instructional designers, assisting them in creating active, engaging, and authentic learning environments that facilitate effective learning experiences. This is achieved by selecting instructional strategies that align with learning activities and learning technologies to achieve the intended outcomes (Dabbagh et al., 2019).

The MOL design framework promotes learning through active participation. It encompasses five attributes of MOL, which are: active, constructive, cooperative, authentic, and intentional learning. Firstly, active learning encourages learners' engagement in an active learning environment by designing various assignments and activities that involve them actively in the learning process. This includes strategies, learning activities, and the use of learning technologies, such as collaborative learning, discussions, role-play, exploration, and problem-solving. The second attribute is constructive learning, which encourages learners to construct knowledge based on their own understanding and become co-producers of content. This is achieved

through performance-based assessment and strategies like reflection, problem-solving, explanation, and articulation. Cooperative learning is the third attribute, fostering engagement in discussions and negotiations to distribute and share knowledge among learners. The fourth attribute is authentic learning, which immerses learners in real-world settings to experience the learning process within relevant contexts. Various pedagogical models, such as problem-based learning, situated learning, and immersive learning (e.g., virtual reality and gamification), are used to cultivate authentic learning experiences. Finally, intentional learning encourages learners to create tangible products that can be shared beyond the classroom boundaries, such as presentations, projects, and portfolios (Dabbagh et al., 2019).

Literature Review

Designing meaningful and high-quality courses entails the utilization of the principles of constructivist pedagogical models that address theory-practice gaps. The pedagogical models employed in this study in conjunction with the MOL Framework include Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Community of Practice (CoP), and Cognitive Apprenticeship (CA). Each model is discussed in the following section.

Problem-Based Learning

Problem-Based Learning, or PBL, is an innovative approach to teaching and learning that focuses on solving complex problems. It is sometimes referred to as "focused, experiential learning" and is structured around the analysis and solution of complex, real-world issues. This method was initially developed by the McMaster Medical School PBL model in 1974 (Masek & Yamin, 2011). Beyond the medical field, Problem-Based Learning is now widely employed in elementary and secondary schools, business schools, higher education, and various other settings. Unstructured challenges (complex real-world or simulated situations) are used as starting points for the learning process in this approach, which has been called a progressive active learning strategy and learner-centered (Ranggi, Ramli, & Yuliani, 2021). Through guided problem-solving, students engage in Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and acquire the skills necessary to tackle challenges while collaborating in small groups (Helmo-Silver, 2004). Over the past 30 years, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has been successfully implemented and continues to gain popularity across a wide range of academic disciplines. It is a learner-centered instructional (and curriculum) approach that grants students the freedom to conduct research, integrate theory and practice, and apply their knowledge and abilities to develop viable solutions to given problems (Savery, 2006).

PBL was defined by Hmelo-Silver (2004) as an instructional strategy where students learn through guided problem solving that is focused on a complicated challenge with no right or wrong answer. Students determine the knowledge they need to address the intended problem in collaborative groups, engage in self-directed learning, apply their newly acquired knowledge to the issue at hand, and then reflect on their learning and the efficacy of their chosen tactics.

Several authors have examined the essential factors required for successful instruction using a Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach. To ensure the effectiveness of this approach, it is crucial to select ill-defined issues, which are often interdisciplinary in nature, and to have a teacher/ instructor who facilitates the learning process and provides a comprehensive reflection at the end of the learning experience. PBL

employs a variety of techniques that contribute to improving skills such as critical thinking, solving complex real-world problems, proposing and negotiating solutions, using and evaluating appropriate learning resources, cooperative learning, effective communication, and lifelong learning. According to Savery (2006), in PBL students become active learners and problem-solvers who seek to pinpoint the underlying causes and thinking for an effective solution. In addition, they become more motivated to learn, think critically, write better, and improve their communication abilities (Azer, 2001).

Community of Practice

Communities of practice (CoPs) have gained significant attention in education for promoting collaboration and knowledge-sharing among educators and learners. CoPs are groups of individuals who come together to exchange ideas, discuss best practices, and collectively enhance teaching and learning outcomes through ongoing communication (Wenger, 1998). These communities offer teachers and academics informal and designated spaces to share experiences, discuss strategies, and disseminate innovative teaching techniques within higher education (MacGillivray, 2017). CoPs operate as social learning systems, fostering self-awareness, reflective practice, and professional development among educators while providing a platform for investigating and expanding teaching approaches (Bond & Lockee, 2018). Despite their advantages, the informality of CoPs in higher education has raised concerns about their potential impact on formal learning recognition (MacGillivray, 2017).

To create effective CoPs in education, several best practices have been proposed, including diversity and inclusivity to incorporate varied perspectives, multi-channel engagement to reach participants where they are, aligning community goals with member needs, distributing leadership, co-developing shared values and purpose, and establishing clear metrics for success while maintaining an inclusive, flexible structure (ShapingEDU, 2022). These practices emphasize the importance of involving diverse voices, engaging members through various channels, aligning community goals with member needs, and fostering a culture of collaboration and trust.

Overall, CoPs have the potential to transfer how educators and learners collaborate and learn from one another. However, their successful development and sustainability require careful planning, effective leadership, and a commitment to building a culture of trust and openness among members. Educational institutions can play a vital role in supporting CoP development by offering resources, infrastructure, and professional development opportunities for both teachers and learners.

Cognitive Apprenticeship

The apprenticeship model has been a historical means for individuals to acquire new skills even preceding the establishment of universities. This model entails experienced individuals supporting less experienced ones to transfer knowledge and skills, a process recognized for its versatility across various domains (Dennen, 2013). An innovative instructional approach, known as "cognitive apprenticeship," has emerged for American classrooms. Combining aspects of traditional apprenticeship with elements of schooling, cognitive apprenticeship, as proposed by Collins and Kapur (2006), promotes expertise development through guided practice and expert observation, making learners' thought processes transparent and enabling skill refinement. It departs from traditional apprenticeships in three key ways: both teachers and students

make their thinking visible, abstract tasks are embedded in real-world contexts to enhance relevance, and skills acquired are transferable to different tasks (Kurt, 2021).

Cognitive apprenticeship implementation requires teachers to explain task processes, integrate abstract tasks into real-world scenarios, and create diverse situations for skill application. While reading and listening are effective learning methods, cognitive apprenticeship offers an active learning approach that fosters students' ability to learn autonomously, particularly in complex domains requiring advanced problem-solving skills (Collins & Kapur, 2006). Guided by four guiding principles—content and structure, demonstration, coaching, and scaffolding. Cognitive apprenticeship can be employed in various educational settings, including traditional classrooms, online courses, and vocational training programs. It promotes collaboration between teachers and learners, with teachers assuming roles as coaches or facilitators during activities such as project-based learning or simulation-based learning (Bell & Kozlowski, 2002).

Cognitive apprenticeship has numerous benefits, including the engagement of students in problem-solving techniques, encouraging them to articulate their thought processes, fostering self-reflection and personal growth, enhancing motivation and engagement, and improving metacognitive skills (Collins, Brown, & Newman, 1989; Kurt, 2021; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Sawyer, 2006). Furthermore, it enables learners to perceive the relevance of their education by applying acquired knowledge and skills to real-world problems, fostering increased interest and a stronger sense of ownership over the learning process.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in providing guidelines for faculty to redesign their courses using constructive approaches, particularly emphasizing the MOL attributes, within the affiliated university context. Implementing these approaches contributes to the creation of engaging courses and enhances the overall learning experience for students. Additionally, this study's results offer practical insights into redesigning traditional face-to-face courses, utilizing the five attributes of MOL and constructivist pedagogy models such as PBL, CoP, and CA. The selected course in this study serves as a model for other faculty members within the university, as pedagogical approaches like those mentioned are currently lacking in course designs across the institution. Consequently, this study provides evidence-based findings that showcase the outcomes of applying a constructive approach to the redesign of conventional courses.

Furthermore, this research aligns with one of the fundamental principles of instructional design, which is to enhance the quality of courses. In this context, the study contributes to the body of knowledge by shedding light on the implications of instructional design in teaching and learning practices. Lastly, the study examines the concept of establishing connections between assignments within the course, supporting previous research findings regarding the benefits of threading cross assignments to help students connect acquired knowledge with practical skills gained during the course (Al Abri et al., 2022; Srinivasan, 2019).

Methodology

A mixed-method approach was employed to conduct an exploratory case study, which involved the use of various instruments and sources such as a pre-course survey, a

focus group discussion, and an analysis of the course based on the MOL framework. The study focused on undergraduate students enrolled in a face-to-face course at the intended university. The MOL attributes were used to redesign the course with the aim of creating engaging and high-quality learning experiences. Constructivist pedagogical models, including problem-based learning (PBL), the community of practice (CoP), and cognitive apprenticeship (CA), were implemented in the selected course.

PBL was defined as an instructional strategy in which students learn through guided problem-solving focused on complex challenges with no right or wrong answers (Hmelo-Silver, 2004). A CoP is a group of people who exchange ideas, discuss best practices, and collectively work towards improving teaching and learning outcomes while engaging in ongoing communication (Wenger, 1998). Cognitive apprenticeship is a teaching method that helps learners develop expertise in a particular field through guided practice and the observation of experts (Dennen, 2013).

By applying the meaningful online learning framework to the course curriculum, this study aimed to investigate its impact on students' learning experiences. The findings and analysis from this exploration may provide valuable insights into design principles that faculty can utilize to develop effective courses in various formats, including online, blended, and face-to-face formats. Ultimately, the outcome of this exploratory study is to offer design principles that can serve as guidelines for designing courses that are engaging and effective across different delivery modes.

Research Questions

The guiding research questions for this study are as follows:

- Q1. How is the Meaningful Online Learning Framework applied to redesign the course curriculum?
- Q2. What is the impact of applying Meaningful Online Learning Framework to the course curriculum on students' learning experiences?
- Q3. What are the design principles for creating a meaningful learning environment?

Context

This study was conducted in the context of the Educational Technology course in Oman, which aims to equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to integrate technology into teaching and learning practices. The selected course was designed based on the barriers and issues educators encounter when integrating technology into their practices. The end goal was to develop and design an effective solution for a specific issue around technology integration in teaching and learning practices by applying one of the constructivist pedagogical models (PBL, CoP, or CA). The course was delivered in a face-to-face format and included both theoretical and practical components. The course included individual and collaborative activities, as well as performance-based assessments.

Sample of the study

In Spring 2023, 11 undergraduate students who enrolled in the TECH4000 course were the participants of this study. The student group included six females and 16 males. Most of the students were in the program's first and second years. It is important to note that all of these students were introduced to these models for the first time. Many students needed more confidence in speaking and participating in discussions. Their English language proficiency levels ranged from beginner to intermediate, which contributed to their hesitation in actively engaging in the

classroom environment. As a result, designing engaging learning experiences might encourage students for better collaboration among students and instructor as well.

Procedures

In Spring 2023, the instructor of the course (the first author of this paper) introduced the study's objectives to the class, which were to examine new teaching strategies and methodologies for mastering the required skills and knowledge of the course using the MOL framework. Student consent was obtained and approved. Consequently, during the first class of the course, students completed the pre-course survey. At the end of the course, a focus group discussion was conducted online with students using Google Meet, lasting for thirty minutes. Finally, the course curriculum was analyzed based on the principles of the MOL attributes, and the report was written.

Data Collection

The data collection for this study included a survey containing open- and closed-ended questions that took 5-10 minutes to complete, and a focus group discussion that lasted approximately 30 minutes. A consent was discussed with students prior to the survey and focus group discussion. It was explained to students that their participation is voluntary and will not affect their grades in the course. They can withdraw from the participation at any time. In addition, the aim of the study was introduced to students, which is to improve the course curriculum and examine the effectiveness of teaching this course with using the selected models as well as the implementation of the MOL principles. The online survey was administered to students at the beginning of the course through Google Form. The survey examined students' awareness about the models that will be employed in designing the content of the course, PBL, CoP, & CA. Also, the survey used to explore if students experienced building learning environments based on these models. Then, at the end of the course, a focus group discussion was conducted that lasted for 30 minutes to understand their perceptions about the topic they studied and its impact of mastering the required skills and knowledge of the course content. The discussion was conducted in Arabic language since most students' find difficulties in explaining their thoughts in English. Finally, a course analysis was used to extract the implementation of the attributes of MOL principles and pedagogical models in the course activities and assignments. In the end, the areas of strength and weakness were identified to fill in the gaps. To ensure that the course curriculum aligns with best practices for creating meaningful learning, the course instructors utilised the principles of the Meaningful Online Learning (MOL) framework to guide the development of course activities and assignments.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the survey responses. Thematic analysis was used to analyze data extracted from focus group discussion. The analysis took place after administering the survey and focus group discussion. However, the analysis of the course took place at the end of the semester. For analyzing the focus group discussion, the transcribing was in Arabic language, then was translated to English. After that, codes were generated and classified under broader themes, which are the organizational codes. Finally, the course curriculum was analyzed based on the five attributes of MOL. At the end, the findings were finalized to reach the conclusion of this study.

Result

Survey Findings

Eleven students responded to the pre-survey, which was administered at the beginning of the course semester. The results showed that the majority of participants have no idea about the constructivist pedagogical models, PBL, CoP, and CA. (58%) of the participants did not learn about PBL, (91%) did not learn about CoP and CA (as shown in Fig.1). Regarding the application of these models in previous models, the results showed that there was no prior experience in applying these models in other courses.

Did you learn about Problem-Based learning in any previous courses ?
12 responses

Did you learn about a Community of Practice in any previous courses ?
12 responses

Did you learn about a cognitive apprenticeship in any previous courses
12 responses

Figure 1. Participants' prior knowledge about PBL, CoP, and CA

Focus Group Findings

An inductive thematic analysis was used as a technique for analyzing the data of the focus group discussion. Three major themes were obtained: (1) Students' perception about the course, (2) the course's assignments, and (3) the teaching strategies

implemented in teaching the course. The three themes indicated how much students were engaged in the course, working collaboratively on their assignments, and acquiring new skills and knowledge at the end of the course.

Students' Perception About the Course

As the semester neared its conclusion, students were asked about their thoughts on this course. All participants acknowledged its benefits and its positive impact on their knowledge and skills. They reported that it covered advanced and essential concepts in the field of educational technology. One student pointed out that "I have taken the course twice and noticed a difference between the two times. There are many concepts and topics that I understood better than the previous time and I learned a lot from it". This finding approves that using MOL principles and constructive approach promote acquiring new skills and innovating new teaching strategies, which is consistent with those of Al Abri et al., (2022) and Knorn, Topalovic, & Varagnolo (2022).

On the other hand, students encountered some difficulties while taking the course. Most of them emphasized that the language used in the course was somewhat advanced compared to their proficiency level, and at times, it was challenging for them to understand certain terminology. One student suggested that it would be better if the course were bilingual, stating, "If the course could be presented in both languages or if the language used was less complex." This suggestion can be justified by the fact that students are more accustomed to simpler language, and some teachers tend to mix Arabic and English when teaching their courses, contributing to the students' challenges with the English language.

The Course Assignments

Regarding the course's assignments, participants were asked about the practical tasks and projects they completed during the semester. They pointed out that they acquired various skills through these assignments, including problem-solving, research, teamwork, and the ability to cite and reference sources in APA style. They emphasized that the assignments helped them conduct research using tools like Google Scholar and the university database, enabling them to write scientific papers following APA style guidelines. As one student remarked, "Correct citation and reference writing in APA style is a new skill that I learned through this assignment." This finding is particularly significant, as it reinforces the value of this skill in academic settings. It aligns with previous research indicating that assignments of this nature can enhance students' writing skills (Graff, Birkenstein, & Maxwell, 2014).

Besides, students learned how to write an essay, how to conduct critical analysis papers, and how to present various points of view on any problem they are discussing. Regarding problem-solving skills, one student illustrated that: "I acquired the skills needed to propose solutions for each problem, define the problem, and utilize the information gathered to find appropriate solutions." Furthermore, students emphasized the demanding nature of these tasks and highlighted the importance of collaboration. They made sure that each student played a specific role and had designated tasks, resulting in more efficient work completion. Another student elaborated on this, stating, "Teamwork allowed us to divide tasks within the team, with each member executing their responsibilities in a coordinated manner. I benefited from my colleagues in terms of coordination, work design, and gained new ideas and skills from the rest of the team members." One interesting observation is that working on assignments can enhance students' learning skills. This finding is also supported by Tuckman's (1965) stages of group development, which suggest that when students

collaborate, they progress through various stages, including forming, storming, norming, and performing. During the norming and performing stages, group members collaborate effectively to achieve their goals, resulting in improved learning outcomes (Tuckman, 1965).

When the students were asked about their awareness of problems related to the first assignment before its implementation, it became evident that using a problem-based learning pedagogy was instrumental in identifying the challenges educators face when integrating technology into the classroom. They affirmed that the assignment aided them in pinpointing the problems and exploring various solutions. They elaborated on how this approach allowed them to gain a realistic understanding of these issues in real-world scenarios. One student mentioned, "This model enabled us to assess the problem initially and then search for authentic examples of these issues within a real context." Additionally, some students mentioned that at the outset of the assignment, they anticipated encountering problems but lacked specific details, and the assignment helped them delve into these issues. Others were already aware of certain issues beforehand, but they discovered additional problems during their research and work on the assignment. Another student emphasized, "Some problems were known in advance, but others emerged during the research and assignment process, which I had not previously noticed."

Furthermore, participants were asked about the sufficiency of the assignment instructions. One student stated that the written instructions for the assignments were clear, and any ambiguities were effectively addressed through oral explanations provided by the instructors. Nevertheless, she suggested that the instructions could be enhanced by including examples from previous assignments. Other students agreed on that the instructions were generally clear but noted that certain aspects required more elaboration and examples, especially given that the projects were novel, and there were no prior examples to reference. This observation is justified by the fact that the MOL framework was being employed for the first time in teaching this course, as well as both content and strategies are entirely new. Consequently, there were no previous students' work to provide as reference for the current students.

During the discussion session, learners reached a consensus on the interconnection between the assignments in the course. Students valued this connection as it proved to be instrumental in bridging the gap between the knowledge and skills they had acquired throughout the course. They expressed that this linkage facilitated the synthesis of information and bolstered their comprehension of the topics they were studying. Furthermore, having insights from prior assignments proved to be a valuable resource in tackling subsequent ones. Additionally, students perceived that the correlation between assignments streamlined the initiation of each new task. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Al Abri, Bannan, and Dabbagh on the adoption of the threading concept across assignments (2022). In their study, they underscored the significance of a specific assignment that focused on the development of the educational environment, a unique objective not addressed in any other course. One student emphasized that Assignment 2 played a pivotal role in addressing this novel goal of educational environment development, which was not covered in any other courses. Furthermore, students pointed that the assignments closely aligned with the course objectives and outcomes, enabling them to attain a deeper understanding of the topics under study. This result is in accord with a recent study indicating that redesigning redesign a classic control course at TU Berlin based on constructive

approach has proven effective in increasing student engagement and promoting active participation throughout the course (Knorn et al., 2022).

Finally, the students highlighted some of the difficulties they face in implementing the assignments, such as a lack of resources and time. They also noted the importance of providing examples in helping them understand the assignments. Overall, the results showed that course assignments can be a good way to help students learn more and improve their skills, especially when they are set up with clear goals and instructions and use active learning techniques like conversation and peer teaching.

Teaching Strategies

Students found the teaching methods employed in this course to be useful and expressed a desire to see them implemented in other courses. Additionally, they generally found the delivery mode of this course, with theoretical instruction in one class and practical application in the subsequent class, to be both feasible and beneficial for acquiring the necessary skills. Students explained that the practical component helped clarify concepts and ideas introduced during the theoretical phase. One student elaborated, stating, "It is very useful. When we were studying certain concepts in the theoretical part, I didn't grasp them fully. However, as we transitioned to the practical part and began applying these ideas and concepts, they started to become clearer."

Furthermore, students appreciated the incorporation of various learning strategies, such as discussions and peer teaching, in the course, as these strategies facilitated more active participation and engagement with the material. They noted that discussions helped overcome shyness and allowed for the free exchange of ideas and opinions. Additionally, peer teaching proved to be valuable for learning from each other's experiences and perspectives, as one student stated, "Peer tutoring was useful. We learned many things, applications, and experiences from each other." These findings align with existing research suggesting that active learning strategies can significantly enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes. (Graff et al., 2014; Knorn et al., 2022).

These findings are consistent with research in educational psychology and instructional design. Best practices in education, which stress the importance of active learning and social interactions for supporting deep learning and understanding of complex ideas, are also in line with these ideas. Social learning theory posits that students can learn from each other when they talk to each other and teach each other. These strategies get students involved with the information and let them build their own understanding of it. This can help them remember and use what they've learned better. Using discussion and peer teaching can also help students learn how to communicate and work together, which are skills that are useful outside of the classroom. The fact that students said discussion helped them get over their shyness and share their ideas and opinions is especially interesting because it suggests that these strategies can help create a positive learning environment where all students feel safe contributing to class discussions. This result supports previous research on that social and cognitive presence should be integrating in designing courses to increase active participation of students (Smadi, Chamberlain, Shifaza, & Hamiduzzaman, 2021).

Course Analysis

To redesign the current course in line with the intended aim of this study, an evaluation of the existing curriculum was conducted to identify areas for improvement. The course primarily focused on the exploration of educational technology implementation

in Oman, the examination of barriers to technology integration, and the discussion of strategies to overcome these challenges. Additionally, students engaged in discussions regarding various approaches to the diffusion and adoption of new technologies in both learning and teaching practices.

The course was designed based on the principles of MOL, involving a re-evaluation of the curriculum's content, assessments, instructional strategies, and learning activities. The application of the five attributes of MOL was integral to this process, and an alignment grid encompassing topics, learning experiences, reading resources, and assessments was developed (as illustrated in Table 1 – Appendix 1). Moreover, weekly learning outcomes were established to ensure the incorporation of MOL attributes into the course. The results of MOL approach are described below.

Active learning: Students actively participate in various in-class activities and assignments designed to encourage their engagement in the learning process. For the main three assignments of this course, students collaborated in pairs. Additionally, they participated in online discussion forums, where they critiqued and analysed case studies relevant to the course material. They also delved into the challenges educators face when integrating learning technology into the classroom, applying scientific research methods to solve problems, and offering critiques from various perspectives. Furthermore, students took on the roles of decision-makers responsible for researching, analysing, and proposing solutions to complex problems. Moreover, students watched videos related to different models, after which they were assigned to groups. Each group extracted the principles of one model and shared them with the entire class.

Constructive learning: Students actively participate in constructing knowledge by drawing from their own understanding and taking on the role of co-producers of content through performance-based assessments. The three main assignments involved students working in groups to: (1) Identify obstacles and challenges related to technology integration in Omani Schools or the University, (2) Search for real-world examples of constructivist pedagogical models and critically assess the extent to which they reflect the principles of the selected model, and (3) Develop and design a constructivist pedagogical model as a solution for the identified issue. The first assignment was presented in the form of a Problem-Based Learning (PBL) format, as depicted in Fig. 2, aiming to immerse students in an authentic PBL environment. Throughout these assignments, students became co-creators of knowledge. They articulated their insights and analyses through argumentative essays addressing the issues in assignment 1, and then proceeded to develop proposals for resolving these issues and designing a website to showcase their solutions. The solutions could encompass Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Communities of Practice (CoP), Computer-Assisted (CA) approaches, or professional development initiatives. Students exercised autonomy in their learning, including the freedom to choose solutions and the agency to complete these assignments. Furthermore, students actively engaged in articulating their thoughts and understanding, while also delivering presentations to showcase their work.

Cooperative learning: In this course, students had the opportunity to work both individually and collaboratively. They engaged individually by participating in discussion forums and peer teaching activities, where students presented and shared trends in learning technologies with the class. Additionally, they worked in groups to complete assignments and prepare presentations for field visits to the Educational Centre at the affiliated university and the school in Finland.

Authentic learning: Students actively immersed themselves in understanding the real-world challenges that educators in the country encounter when integrating technology into their teaching practices. Furthermore, they conducted research to find and analyse a real-life example from one of the models, such as PBL, CoP, or CA. As previously mentioned, students also had the opportunity to experience a PBL environment in assignment 1.

Assignment 1

Learning outcome: To determine the issues teachers in K-12 or instructors at the university encounter in integrating technology effectively in teaching and learning practices.

Technology is rapidly evolving in every aspect of our life. Education has been affected by this rapid change in technology. As a result, governments should enforce educational institutions to integrate technology in their teaching and learning practices. Especially with the experience the educators, teachers, and professors have acquired during the pandemic in 2020-2022. However, educators and teachers encounter difficulties and challenges in integrating technology into the classroom effectively. Your task is to work in groups. You will collaborate, research, and determine the issues or challenges that hinder those teachers and educators from using educational technology successfully in their teaching and learning practices. At the end of this task, each group will provide a report of their findings of the issues teachers in K-12 or instructors at the university encounter in integrating technology effectively in teaching and learning practices. Propose solutions to solve the identified issue.

Deliverable product: A report of 3-5 pages demonstrates the arguments and discussion about the issues of technology integration in teaching and learning practices. The report should include the arguments and discussion found in research about issues; define the issues; and propose solutions for these issues. Don't forget that these found issues are evidence-based. So, you need to include the citation of these issues (similar to research papers).

Instructions (Steps to follow):

- Examine and define the problem.
- Explore what you already know about the underlying problem.
- Determine what you need to learn and where you can search for the information necessary to solve the problem.
- Use the provided resources in addition to your own search.
- Also, consider to interview teachers in schools and instructors in the university
- Solve the problem.
- Report your findings.
- Evaluate the possible ways to solve the problem
- Present your finding for the class.

Aids for argument and discuss the issues: <https://www.phrasebank.manchester.ac.uk/referring-to-sources/>

Figure 2. Assignment 1: Building PBL Environment

Intentional learning: The final assignment was a project in which students formulated a proposal to address the issues identified in assignment 1. Furthermore, they were tasked with designing and constructing a website to showcase their chosen solution. This signifies that by the conclusion of this course, students generated a tangible product that can be shared beyond the confines of the classroom, consisting of both a proposal and a website.

Design Principles of Creating Meaningful Learning Environment

Creating a meaningful learning environment involves designing an experience that engages and motivates learners to accomplish their learning outcomes. The following design principles have been developed based on focus group discussions and course

analysis data. These design principles serve as guiding principles for faculty to create engaging courses. The design principles are as follows:

Courses should be designed based on a learner-centred approach.

The desired course objectives should be established to define the learning outcomes and assessment methods for the students in the course.

The course curriculum design should prioritize encouraging learners to become active participants in the learning process by providing opportunities for them to engage in activities such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making.

The learning experiences of courses should create opportunities for learners to collaborate and learn from one another through activities such as group projects and discussions.

Real-world examples and scenarios should be provided to illustrate the relevance of the learning material and how it can be applied in practical settings.

Learners should receive immediate and constructive feedback on their performance to help them understand their progress and areas for improvement.

The courses should be redesigned with authentic assessments that assess learners' abilities to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations rather than just memorizing information.

Designing courses to be active, constructive, cooperative, authentic, and intentional.

Protecting Human Subject: Reliability and Trustworthiness

Ethical approval for conducting this study was obtained from the scientific research committee at the researcher's university prior to commencing any data collection procedures. Any information shared throughout this study must be held in strict confidentiality. In this study, the only information collected from the participants was derived from the pre-course survey and focus group discussions, which were accessible only to the researchers and utilized exclusively for research purposes. The raw data is securely stored on the researchers' computer with password protection for a period of 5 years, after which the data will be permanently deleted. To ensure privacy, pseudonyms were employed to present the results of the collected data, preventing the disclosure of any identifiable information (Maxwell, 2013).

To mitigate potential conflicts of interest, given that the first author of this study served as the course instructor and was actively involved in conducting the research, the second researcher conducted the focus group discussions with students and handled data analysis. A third researcher independently reviewed the study's results to enhance research subjectivity.

The research methodology employed in this study is a mixed-method approach. To validate the findings, the researchers utilized peer review and triangulation as recommended by Glesne (2016). Specifically, the use of focus groups in this study contributes to external validity, as these groups involve individuals discussing their experiences related to the course within a social context rather than a purely personal one, further supporting the study's credibility.

Conclusion

This exploratory study aimed to investigate the impact of modifying the pedagogy of a course on student engagement and learning experiences. The findings of this study demonstrated that incorporating the attributes of Meaningful Online Learning into the course curriculum led to enhanced learning experiences and the acquisition of new skills and knowledge. Students construct knowledge through authentic assessments and learning activities such as collaborative work and discussions. These findings are exemplified as follows: Active learning is emphasized through in-class activities, group assignments, case study analysis, and problem-solving. Students also watch videos on various models and share the principles they extract in groups with the entire class. In constructive learning, students actively construct knowledge and collaborate in groups to complete three main assignments focused on technology integration challenges. These assignments involve problem-based learning (PBL) and require students to write argumentative essays and propose solutions, fostering their ownership, agency, and presentation skills. In cooperative learning, students engaged in both individual and collaborative learning experiences. They individually participated in discussion forums and peer teaching activities, while also working in groups for assignments. In addition, students engaged in authentic learning by exploring real-world challenges faced by educators when integrating technology. They also analysed models like PBL, CoP, and CA and experienced a PBL environment in one of their assignments. Furthermore, they practiced intentional learning through a final project, where they developed proposals and websites as tangible solutions to the issues identified in assignment 1, creating products that could be shared beyond the classroom.

As far as the theory-practice gap is concerned, this design of this course using MOL attributes offering theoretical and practical classes, enabling students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts. The finding of this study highlighted the significance of establishing connections across assignments within the course and fostering collaborative work. Students highly appreciated this link because it effectively bridged the gap between the knowledge and skills they had gained during the course. They found that this connection helped them synthesize information and enhance their understanding of the subjects they were learning. Moreover, having insights from previous assignments turned out to be a valuable asset when dealing with future ones. Additionally, students believed that the relationship between assignments made it easier to start each new task.

Additionally, the study proposed eight design principles that can serve as a valuable guide for improving student success by redesigning courses across various delivery modes. However, it is important to note that these design principles were derived from a limited number of participants, necessitating further investigation with diverse participants across different courses to refine and validate these principles. The design principles identified from this study for courses design include learner-centeredness, Clearly defined course objectives help students understand what they should learn and how their knowledge will be assessed, promoting active participation, fostering collaboration, using real-world examples, providing immediate feedback, and emphasizing authentic assessments, instead of just memorization, assessments should evaluate students' ability to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations. These principles collectively emphasize making courses dynamic, engaging, collaborative, real-world-oriented, and purposeful for effective learning.

This study faced two main limitations. Firstly, the sample size was small, with only 11 students enrolled in the Spring 2023 course. Secondly, the approach implemented was

new and there were no prior examples of constructivist pedagogical models to assist students in completing their assignments.

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Authors

Maimoona H. Al Abri holds PH. D in Education with specialization of Learning Technologies Design Research from George Mason University, USA, and an MEd in Learning Technology from Griffith University, Australia. She is an assistant professor in Instructional and Learning Technology Department at Sultan Qaboos University. She was the director of the Educational Technology Department in the Ministry of Education in the Sultanate of Oman since 2013. Also, was a co-leader of Government Community of Practice at the Metro DC Chapter in the Association for Talent Development in United States. She introduced the concept of integrating ICT into k-12 education in MOE Oman and has led the establishment of the first digital school in Muscat Region. She led several crucial projects such as digitizing the national curriculum, developing an e-learning strategy in k-12, and developing the national policy for OER in education. In 2017, she was nominated for Kappa Delta Pi (Education Honor Society) and became a DOER (Designing with OER) Fellow in USA. Maimoona's research interests include meaningful online learning, open educational resources, open educational practices, open pedagogy, user experience design, design thinking, learning theories, and technology integration in schools.

Asma Y. Al. Aamri is currently a PhD student in the Learning, Design, and Technology (LDT) department at Mary Frances Early College of Education, University of Georgia (UGA), USA (2023–2027). She holds bachelor's and master's degrees in ILT from Sultan Qaboos University. She works as a lecturer in the Instructional and Learning Technology (ILT) Department at the College of Education at Sultan Qaboos University. She worked as an Information Technology Curricula Specialist at the Ministry of Education. Her research interests include emergence technologies like learning analytics and AI, e-learning, e-training, instructional design, and project-based learning. She has various academic achievements, as she has participated in many conferences locally and internationally and published many research papers in refereed scientific journals. One of her research papers is in the field of 3D virtual learning environments, and it has received more than 10 citations in less than a year and a half. She is the owner of "MODREN," which is a social media initiative aimed at raising awareness about technology integration in teaching and learning, sharing professional experience, and providing educational technology content.

Abdelrahman Mohamed Ahmed El-haj is an associate professor of educational technology, with over 18 years of experience in teaching graduate and undergraduate courses in the areas of instructional design, information and communication technologies, and research in educational technology. His current areas of research include technology integration, Social media, mobile learning, e-learning, distance education, and use of web 2.0 technologies in education.

Appendix 1

Table 1. An Alignment Between Topics, Learning Experiences, Reading Resources and Assessments

Week no.	Topics	Learning Activities	Reading & Resources (Reading should be completed prior class)	Assessment & Evidence	Weekly Outcomes
Week1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course Introduction • Syllabus overview Respond to pre-survey	Meet & Greet Introduce students to the MOL research study and get their consent to their participation in the study. Administer students to the pre=survey	Course Syllabus Pre-survey: https://forms.gle/htdNMAyVENzFWJ2v7	Discussion Forum: What do expect to learn from this course	Explore course syllabus.
Week2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology integration in education: Definitions, Benefits & Challenges 	Large group discussion: instructor will direct students toward discussion in class about the reading. Small group discussion: Students will work in groups to discuss	Reading: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does “technology integration” mean? • What Is Successful Technology Integration? • 7 Benefits of Technology Integration in the Education Sphere • Understanding the relationship between teachers’ pedagogical beliefs and technology use in education 	Graded task (1): In discussion forum, respond to the prompts in Moodle.	Define technology integration in education effectively. Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of technology integration in education successfully